

INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA KOMPLIMENTNI IFODALOVCHI VOSITALAR

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Toshkent shahar Sergeli tumani 55-sonli umumta'lim maktabi ingliz tili fani
o'qituvchilari

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillarida komplimentni ifodalovchi vositalari hamda ingliz va o'zbek kommunikativ madaniyatida kompliment va uning qo'llanilishi va komplimentning funksiyalari va uning klassifikatsiyasi tahlil qiliniladi.

Kalit so'zlar: «kompliment», maqtov, xushomad, kommunikativ madaniyat, minnatdorchilik, nutqning leksik va sintaktik tuzilishini, kompliment turlari.

СРЕДСТВА КОМПЛИМЕНТА В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются средства выражения комплиментов в английском и узбекском языках, а также комплименты и их применение в английской и узбекской коммуникативной культуре, а также функции комплиментов и их классификация.

Ключевые слова: «комплимент», похвала, комплимент, коммуникативная культура, благодарность, лексико-синтаксический строй речи, виды комплиментов.

MEANS OF COMPLIMENT IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Abstract. This article analyzes the means of expressing compliments in English and Uzbek, as well as compliments and their application in English and Uzbek communicative culture, and the functions of compliments and their classification.

Keywords: "compliment", praise, compliment, communicative culture, gratitude, lexical and syntactic structure of speech, types of compliments.

KIRISH

«Kompliment» tushunchasi barcha tillarga xos tushuncha bo'lsada xar bir tilda o'ziga xos ifodalanishga egadir. «Kompliment» tushunchasining moxiyatini chuqur o'rganish uchun, avvalo tilshunoslik fanida rivojlanib kelayotgan kognitiv tilshunoslik va lingvomadaniyatshunoslik fanlaridagi nazariya va qarashlarni o'rganib chiqish lozim.

J. Xolms, P. Braun va N. Wolfson komplimentativ bayonotlarni o'rganish davomida kompliment ko'plab illukativ funktsiyalarini ifodalashi mumkinligini aniqlashdi. Ushbu olimlar komplementni keltirilgan vaziyatlarda masalan: tabriklarda, minnatdorchiliklarda, uzr so'ralganda, salomlashishlarda qo'llash mumkin deb aytadilar

Misol uchun, ushbu holatda, Emmi ishlarni tashkillashtirish va rejalashtirish qobiliyati uchun tabrik qabul qiladi. Komplimentni ifodalash uchun, ijobiy bahoga ega bo'lgan "excellent" sifati ishlatiladi.

"I congratulate you. Your organization must have been indeed **excellent**." Emily Carnaby shunday dedi:

"Amy was always **good at organization**. Our father – he was the Vicar of Kellington in Essex- always said that Amy had quite a genius for planning. She always made all the arrangements for the Social and the Bazaars and all that"

Ana endi, salomlashish holatini tasavvur qiling. Shunday qilib, xonimni kutib olish uchun, janob bu uchrashuvning ahamiyatililigini va muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Bu erda "brilliant" sifati ishlatiladi.

" Everyone is dying to know **the brilliant Mrs. Cheveley**."

"Thank you, Sir Robert. An acquaintance that begins with a compliment is sure to develop into a real friendship. It straits in the right manner.

Minnatdarchilik holatini ifodalash uchun undov gaplarni "good" sifati bilan qo'llaymiz

" Lady Chiltren, I have a certain amount of very news to tell you. Mrs cheveley gave me up Robert's letter last night, and I burnt it. Robert is safe."

" Safe! Oh! I'm so glad of that! What **a good friend** you are to him- to us!"

TADQIQOT MATERIALLARI VA METODOLOGIYASI

V.V. Leontyev nutq jarayonining har xil tasnifida maqtov, xushomad va komplimentlarning o'rni haqida savol berdi. Tadqiqotchi o'z oldiga maqtov, xushomad va kompliment o'rtasidagi o'xshashlik va katta kategorik farqlarni aniqlash vazifasini qo'yadi. Ushbu tushunchalarni solishtirib, V.V. Leontyev ularning har biri uchun alohida farqlovchi xususiyatlarni ochib beradi va bu tushunchalar bir-biriga to'liq mos kelmasligini ta'kidlaydi, chunki ularning har biri o'z o'ziga xos maqsadlarga ega.. Uchchala tahlil qilinayotgan tushunchalar muallif tomonidan baholovchi bayonotlar bilan bevosita va to'g'ridan-to'g'ri bog'liq bo'lgan hissiy tushunchalar sifatida taqdim etiladi. Leontyevning ta'rifiga ko'ra kompliment maqtovdan ustun turadi va hurmatni ifodalaydi. Komplimentni ko'rib chiqishning bunday yondashuvi, bizga komplimentni ijobiy his-tuyg'ular bilan ifodalaydi.

A.V. Bobenko, ingliz tilida koplimentning asosiy vazifasi bir nechta va o'ziga xos namoyondalarga ega ekanligini ta'kidlaydi. Misol uchun, kompliment ko'pincha minnatdorchilik sifatida qo'llaniladi, masalan:

"I didn't want to go without thanking you for all **your kindness to me**," U dedi.

"Oh, that's all right."

Komplimentni salomlashish o'rnida ham qo'llash mumkin bunga misol uchun:

"Good evening, **dear Gertrude!** so kind of you to let, me bring my friend, Mrs. Cheveley.

Two such charming women should know each other!"

Kompliment ko'pincha suhbat boshlanishining ham sababchisi bo'ladi, masalan:

"**How is the most charming woman in the world?**"

(Missis Allonbi xonim Lut Stutfildni qo'lidan ushlab)

"We are both quite well, thank you, Lord Illingworth."

Spiker komplimentni rag'batlantirish uyg'otish maqsadida ham foydalanishi mumkin masalan:

" Well, what do you think? "

" The play's all right. I don't see how it can fail to be a success" He caught something doubtful in her tone.

"What's wrong then? **The part's wonderful. I mean, it's a wonderful part, I know that.**".

Ko'pincha, kompliment -bu tanqidni yumshatishning bir yo'li, masalan:

"Do you know the promoter says we played nine minutes longer tonight, they laughed so much."

"Seven curtain calls. I thought the public were going on all night." Well, you've only got to blame yourself, darling. There's no one in the world who could have given the performance you gave tonight.

Ushbu ma'lumotlarga asoslanib, tadqiqotchi komplimentni ingliz tilida ko'p funktsional xususiyatga ega deb hisoblaydi, unda komplimentning asosiy funktsiyasi, kommunikatorlar o'rtasidagi do'stona munosabatlarni o'rnatish va qo'llab-quvvatlashdir.

A.V. Kolegaevaning so'zlariga ko'ra, kompliment muloqotda ajralmas qismi bo'lib, ko'pincha ma'ruzachining ijobiy holatlariga: sevgi, hayrat, hurmat, g'urur va hokazolarni aks ettiradi. Tadqiqotchi komplimentning quyidagi turlarini aniqlaydi:

1) yo'q odamga qaratigan kompliment. Ushbu misolda qo'shiqchining chiroyli ovozi kompliment sifatida qayd etilgan:

"His name" said aunt Kate" was Parkiston. I heard him when he was ever put into a man's throat."

"Strange", said Mr. Bartell D'Arcy. "I never even heard of him."

"Yes, yes, Miss Morkan is right," said Mr. Browne. "I remember hearing of old Parkiston, but he's too far back for me."

"A beautiful, pure, sweet, mellow English tenor," said Aunt Kate with enthusiasm.

2) tasniflovchi komplimentda o'zgaralar so'zi bilan iltifot qilinadi. Bu yerda qizning biznes qobiliyati uchun kompliment qilinadi:

"You'll have to help me to find something really nice to put it its place." "Mary has a wonderful eye, did you know that, Bob? She ought to go into business with me."

Komplimentni o'rganish nutqning leksik va sintaktik tuzilishini, shuningdek, uning funktsiyalarini aniqlash bilangina chegaralanmaydi.

N. Wolfson komplimentni ikkita asosiy aniq guruhlarga bo'ladi:

1) Tashqi ko'rinishga nisbatan kompliment:

"You are a terribly attractive woman."

2) Qabul qiluvchilarning qobiliyatlariga nisbatan kompliment:

"You've made a tremendous success with my people. They've taken an enormous fancy to you."

«God, Five worked for it," thought Julia.

R.V. Serebryakova komplimentni yanada kengroq va batafsil taklif qiladi. R.V. Serebryakova, ingliz kommunikativ madaniyatida komplimentlardan foydalanish bir xil emas deb hisoblaydi. R.V. Serebryakova kompliment turlarining nutqda ishlatilish foizini ushbu jadvalda ko'rishimiz mumkin.

R.V. Serebryakova ingliz kommunikativ madaniyatida odamning ichki axloqiy xususiyatlariga bo'lgan komplimentlar birinchi o'rinda turadi deb aytadi. Avvalambor, komplimentlar o'zining mehr-oqibat, saxiylik, halollik, kamtarlik, jasorat, dindorlikligi bilan ajralib turadi. Masalan:

1) *"Dear Sally, what I like about you is your beautiful honesty."*

2) "Life is like that all the way through, isn't it? Certain things happen because people are in a certain spot at a certain time."

"But what you did was wonderful."

"I was over-bold. I hesitated for a while but something told me that Daniel loved you enough, was strong enough. **You are lucky** to be his wife, Rachel. He is the one who has done so much for you, not I.

"Daniel feels the same as I do about you,"

"I'm glad it's gratifying to take a bold step and right."

"We have been so lucky, and but for you..." she shivered

"**You are doubly lucky** because you realize how lucky you are. So many people don't."¹

3) Norman had the dressing-table made for her (his wife) soon after they were married. It had been made by a native carpenter of course, and they had had the mirror sent from Singapore, but it was made for her own design, of the exact size and shape she wanted, with plenty of room for all her toilet things and her make up. She remembered still how pleased she was when first she had it. She threw her arms round her husband's neck and kissed him. "Oh Norman, you are good to me," she said, "I'm a lucky little girl to have caught a chap like you, aren't I?"²

Suhbatdoshning tashqi ko'rinishni ifodalash uchun speker ko'plab sifatlarni qo'llashi masalan: beautiful, pretty, wonderful, graceful, gorgeous, sweet, nice, fine.

1) **You will always be as pretty as possible.**³

2) "What wonderfully blue eyes you have, Ernest! They **are quite, quite, blue**. I hope you'll always look at me just like that, especially when there are other people present."⁴

1) "Cecily, ever since I first looked upon your **wonderful and incomparable beauty**, I have dared to love you **wildly, passionately, devoted, hopelessly.**"

2) "I don't think that you should tell me that you love me wildly, passionately, devotedly, hopelessly. **Hopelessly doesn't seem to make much sense, does it?**" "Cecily!"⁵

Suhbatdoshning kasbiga nisbatan ishlatilgan ko'pgina komplimentlar erkaklarga qaratilgan.

Masalan:

1) "Sir Joseph said frankly: "I know you're **a tip-top man** at this sort of thing. I made inquiries and I was told that you were **the best man available**. I mean to get to the bottom of this business and I don't grudge the expense. That's why I got you to come here."

"**You are fortunate,**" said Hercule Poirot⁶

2) "Lord Illingworth, everyone has been congratulating me, Lady Hunstanton and Lady Caroline, and ...everyone. I hope I'll make a good secretary."

"**You will be a pattern secretary,** Gerald."⁷

Speker o'z fikrini iloji boricha aniqroq bayon qilishga harakat qilayapti, buni biz qisqa so'z birikmalaridan bilib olishimiz mumkin.

¹ Holt V. Seven for a Secret. Fawcett CREST. - New York, 1992. - P. 170-171.

² Maugham S. Flotsam and Jetsam. Stories. - Ленинград, 1976. - P. 32.

³ Wilde O. An Ideal Husband. Plays. - Moscow, 1961. - P. 221.

⁴ Wilde O. The Importance of Being Earnest. Plays. - Moscow, 1961. - P. 295.

⁵ Wilde O. The Importance of Being Earnest. Plays. - Moscow, 1961. - P. 319.

⁶ Christie A. The Nemean Lion. Making It All Right. Modern English Short Stories. - Moscow, 1978. - P. 11.

⁷ Wilde O. A Woman of No Importance. Plays. - Moscow, 1961. - P. 109.

Oila a'zolariga va yaqinlarga qilingan kompliment ingliz kommunikativ madniyatining yorqin belgisidir. Ushbu yo'nalishidagi komplimentni faqatgina do'stlar, qarindoshlar qila oladilar. Bunday muloqatlar suhbatdoshning qanchalar yaqinligini va o'z his tuyg'ularini to'liq ifoda eta olishlarini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

Masalan:

*"I was just saying what a pleasant party you have asked us to meet. You have a wonderful power of selection. It's quite a gift." "Dear Caroline, how kind of you! I think we all do fit in very nicely together."*⁸ Aniq ifoda etilgan ijobiy sifatlar pretty, fine, nice, sweet keng qo'llanilgan, masalan:

"Cecily Gardew? What a very sweet name! Something tells me that we are going to be great friends. I like you already more than I can say. My first impressions of people are never wrong."

*"How nice of you to like me so much after we have known each other such a comparatively short time. Pray sit down."*⁹

Kuchaytiruvchi ravish ishlatilgan: much, extremely, masalan:

*"I'm afraid it's very flattering – I'm not so pretty as that (showing photograph) "You are much prettier. But haven't you got one of yourself with your little boy?"*¹⁰

Ingliz tili nutqida yoshga, ziynatlarga, insonlarning kiyimiga qaratilgan komplimentlar kam qo'llaniladi. Ana shu komplimentlarga misollar keltiramiz:

1) *"And Gt... Gt a little over thirty." "Dear, you look weeks younger than that."*¹¹

2) *"I can show you something that will please you better." She had run up, breathlessly, cut the cords, scattered the tissue paper and yes, there was the very hat - rather large, soft, with a great, curled feather, and a black velvet rose, nothing else. They had been charmed. The girl had put it on and then handed it to Rosabel.*

*"Let me see how it looks on you," she said, frowning a little, very serious indeed. Rosabel turned to the mirror and placed it on her brown hair, then faced them. "Oh, Harry, isn't it adorable" the girl cried. "I must have that!" She smiled again at Rosabel. "It suits you beautifully"*¹²

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI

A.V. Bobenko, turli madaniyatlardagi komplimentlarni taqqoslab ularni o'rganish shuni ko'rsatdiki, bir millatdagi kompliment boshqa millatga to'g'ri kelmasligini aniqladi.¹³ Masalan ko'pgina inglizabon mamlakatlarda (1), (2), (3) chi gaplar kompliment sifatida qabul qilinadi, biroq (4), (5) chi gaplar bundan mustasnodir:

- 1) *I like your hat.*
- 2) *You have the greatest eyes I've ever seen.*
- 3) *You really surprised us with the beautiful song last night.*
- 4) *You must have been exhausted from all that shopping.*
- 5) *That tie you've got on is pure silk, isn't it?*

⁸ Wilde O. A Woman of No Importance. Plays. - Moscow, 1961. - P. 97.

⁹ Wilde O. The Importance of Being Earnest. Plays. - Moscow, 1961. - P. 323-324.

¹⁰ Wilde O. Lady Windermere's Fan. Plays. - Moscow, 1961. - P. 79-80.

¹¹ Wilde O. An Ideal Husband. Plays. - Moscow, 1961. - P. 269.

¹² Mansfield K. The Tiredness of Rosabel. Selected Stories. - Moscow, 1959. - P. 169.

¹³Бобенко А.В. Kompliment как объект лингвистического исследования. Методы лингвистических исследований. ХГПУ, 1997. - С. 78-9.

Indoneziya va Yaponiya mamlakatlarida esa (4), (5) chi gaplar kompliment sifatida qabul qilinadi.

A.V. Bobenko, Amerika ingliz tilida variantida komplimentning eng hayratlanarli xususiyatlaridan biri, ularning aksariyatini "Tashqi ko'rinish" (ayniqsa kiyim va soch) qaratilgan va odatda speaker ayol komplimentni qabul qiluvchidir. J. Manesning ta'kidlashicha, Amerika jamiyatida, o'zlarining va boshqa odamlarning tashqi ko'rinishi e'tibor bo'lishiga ko'proq tashvishlanadigan ayollar va har qanday yoshdagi ayollar jozibador ko'rinishga harakat qilishlari kerak deb hisoblashadi. Quyida keltirilgan misollar ko'roq ayollarda uchraydi hoh ular do'stlar, kasbdoshlar, tasodifiy tanishlar yoki butunlay begonalar bo'lsalar.

1) *"What pretty hair you have," said Julia.*¹⁴

2) *"How sweet you are looking! Where do you get your gowns?"*¹⁵

A.V. Bobenko Amerika jamiyatida kompliment asosan tashqi ko'rinishga qaratiladi. Amerikaliklar tabiatan berilgan chiroyga kompliment qilishni xoxlashmaydi, keng tarqalgan komplimentlar soch turmagiga va chiroyli sochlarga¹⁶.

*"Most women in London, nowadays, seem to furnish their rooms with nothing but orchids, foreigners, and French novels. But here we have the room of a sweet saint. Fresh natural flowers, books that don't shock one, pictures that one can look at without blushing."*¹⁷

Ko'p tilshunoslar qatori R.V. Serebryakova ham kompliment va maqtov o'rtasidagi bog'liqliklarni aniqlaydi va ba'zi hollarda kompliment va maqtov mutloq to'g'ri kelishiga ishonadi.

1-jadval

Kompliment turi	Umumiy foizdan
1 Tashqi ko'rinishiga qaratilgan compliment	15%
2 Yoshga qaratilgan kompliment	6%
3. Ichki, axloqiy fazilatlariga qaratilgan compliment	18%
4 Aqliy qobiliyatlarga qaratilgan kompliment	13%
5 Tashqi ko'rinishning alohida elementlariga qaratilgan compliment	8%
6. Qobiliyatni yoki muayyan kasbni baholovchi komplimentlar	14%
7 Liboslarni ifodalovchi komplimentlar	10%
8 Ziynatlarga nisbatan komplimentlar	2%
9 Nomlarga nisbatan komplimentlar	10 1%
10 Xonadonga, uy sharoitiga nisbatan komplimentlar	3%
11 Umumiy baholovchi komplimentlar	10% ¹⁸

¹⁴ Maugham S. Theatre. Высшая школа. - М., 1985. - P. 137.

¹⁵ Wilde O. Lady Windermere's Fan. Plays. - Moscow, 1961. - P. 39.

¹⁶ Бобенко А.В. Kompliment как объект лингвистического исследования. Методы лингвистических исследований. ХГПУ, 1997. - С. 80.

¹⁷ Wilde O. A Woman of No Importance. Plays. - Moscow, 1961. - P. 152-153.

¹⁸ Серебрякова Р.В. Национальная специфика речевых актов комплимента и похвалы в русской и английской коммуникативных культурах. Дис... канд. филол. наук. - Воронеж, 2001. - С. 2.

MUHOKAMA

Shunday qilib, ingliz tilida muloqot insonning ichki, axloqiy fazilatlariga bo'lgan komplimentlarga asoslanadi, ular barcha qayd etilgan iltifotning 18 foizini tashkil qiladi. Ulardan bir oz kam foizi bilan odamning ko'rinishi o'rin egallagan, 15% va qobiliyatni yoki muayyan kasbni baholovchi komplimentlar 14% Kamdan-kam hollarda ziynatlarga qaratilgan 2%, xonadonga va uy sharoitiga qaratilgan komplimentlar 3% va 1% nomlarga qaratilgan komplimentlar joy egallagan.

O'zbek adabiyotlariga ham nazar solsak misol uchun

“Rahmat so'zdan chetda qoldirmaslik uchun Otabekni ham oraga oldi:

*- Bizning Marg'ilonda bir qiz bor, -dedi- **shundog' ko'hlikki bu o'rtada uning o'xshashi bo'lmas deb o'ylayman**”*¹⁹ Ushbu misolda qizni ijobiy sifatlar bilan ta'riflanmoqda ya'ni qizga nisbatan kompliment ishlatilayapti.

Quyidagi misolda esa bolaning qobiliyatiga nisbatan kompliment qo'llanilyapdi. *“Bir ayol qo'shnisiga aytayapdi:*

*- Maydonchada o'ynayotgan bolalar orasida Boltavoyingizni ko'rdim. **Naq generalning o'zi-ya! Hammaga buyruq beradi: “Sen u yoqqa o't, sen chiqib tur...”** Bola bechoralar ham indamay quloq solishadi.*

*- Mening Boltavoyim-a? mening bolam mo'min qobil. Uyda churq degan ovozi chiqmaydi. Birovga buyruq beradiganlardanmas u.”*²⁰

Keyingi misolda esa qaynota keliniga nisbatan komplimentni qo'llaydi. *“– Bizning Marg'ilonda ham **shunday kelinimiz bor ekan-ku, biz bilmay yurg'an ekammiz-da, - deb tevaragiga qarab kulindi va qo'lini duog'a ochdi. – Bizni shunchalik siylab kelibsizlar, bu yaxshiligingizni bizdan qaytmasa, xudodan qaytsin. Ollah taolo yoshlarga taqabbul duo...**”*²¹

O'zbek tilida kompliment ko'proq qizlarga nisbatan ishlatiladi qizlarning chiroyini ta'riflashda masalan: *“**Qalamda tortilgandek qoshlari, yonib turgan qop-qora xumor ko'zlar, sutday oppoq yuz, ingichka iyagidagi mitti xoli, angishvonadek og'zi**”*²²

- O'qishga kirishda kuchiga sal ishonmay turuvdi...

Xullas, fe'li sal og'irroq....

*- Bu og'irlikni bizga qo'yib beravering. Ukangiz **chidamli yigit**. Hozircha shuning o'zi yetarli. Endi boring. Bu tuynukdan uchib chiqmoqchi bo'lgan qushchalarni hurkitmang*²³

Ushbu misolda yigitga nisbatan chidamli sifati ishlatilgan, uning ichki axloqiy fazilatlariga qilingan iltifot.

Shu kulimsirah bilan yana biroz borgandan keyin bu safar jiddiyroq qilib, dedi:

*- Ahliyimiz ham **uchiga chiqqan chevar, xudoga shukr. Ojizamiz ham do'ppi tikishga “farang” bo'lib chiqdi!***²⁴

¹⁹ Qodiriy A. O'tgan kunlar. Yangi asr avlodi. - T.,2018. – B. 10.

²⁰ Tohir Malik. Alvido... bolalik. Sharq. –T., 2014. - B. 266.

²¹ Qodiriy A. O'tgan kunlar. Yangi asr avlodi. - T.,2018. – B. 373.

²² Hoshimov O'tkir. Ikki eshik orasi. Sharq. –T.,2013. – B. 95.

²³ Tohir Malik. Imtihon. – Toshkent, 2015. – B. 122.

²⁴ Cho'lpon. Kecha va Kunduz. Yangi asr avlodi. T., - 2014. - B. 14.

Bunda biz ayollarning qobiliyati yoki muayyan kasbni bildiruvchi komplimentni ko'rishimiz mumkin.

- *O'lmasxon, bormisiz? Durustroq aytsangizchi!*

Saltining yana bir o'rtog'i – Qumri uning so'zini quvvatladi:

- *Ha, rost, shunday yaxshi ovozingiz bor ekan, sho'x-sho'x aytmaysizmi?*

Keng dalaada qancha cho'zsangiz, shuncha ketadi varanglab....²⁵

Bu misolda qizning qobiliyati shunday yaxshi sifati bilan kompliment qo'llanilgan. Endigi keltiriladigan misolda qizning ichki fazilatlariga qarata ishlatilgan. Masalan:

Hilolaxon oyog'ingiz yengil ekan faqat yutayapmiz qarang deb xushomad qilishdan charchamasdi. Atofida shuncha ...

Yuqorida keltirilgan misollardan shuni bilishimiz mumkinki insonning tashqi ko'rinishiga ishlatiladigan kompliment o'zbek kommunikativ madaniyatida juda keng qo'llaniladi. Biz o'rganish jarayonida O'zbek kommunikativ madaniyatida komplimentlardan foydalanish bir xil emasligini ko'rdik, buni keltirilgan jadvalga qarab bilishimiz mumkin.

2-jadval

Kompliment turi	Umumiy foizdan
Tashqi ko'rinishiga qaratilgan compliment	22%
2 Yoshga qaratilgan kompliment	6%
3. Ichki, axloqiy fazilatlariga qaratilgan compliment	20%
4 Aqliy qobiliyatlarga qaratilgan kompliment	12%
5 Tashqi ko'rinishning alohida elementlariga qaratilgan compliment	4%
6. Qobiliyatni yoki muayyan kasbni baholovchi komplimentlar	15%
7 Liboslarni ifodalovchi komplimentlar	10%
10 Xonadonga, uy sharoitiga nisbatan komplimentlar	2%
11 Umumiy baholovchi komplimentlar	9%

Uyni ko'rib kelgan Olim do'stiga shunday dedi:

- *Uy naq qasrning o'zi-yaa, mebellarni aytmaysanmi yap-yapgi Italiya mebellari²⁶.*

Quyida keltiriladigan misollarda esa insonning ichki fazilatlariga qobiliyatlariga, kasbiga qaratilgan komplimentlardir.

- *Sen bularni boqmoqchimisiz?*

- *Ha, donolarning dono ayoli.*

²⁵ Cho'lpon. Kecha va Kunduz. Yangi asr avlodi. T., - 2014. - B. 23.

²⁶ Tohir Malik. Imtihon. Toshkent. – 2015. - B. 190.

- *Assalomu alaykum, katta savdogar!* – dedi u yarim hazil, yarimchin. – *Karvoning omon –eson yetib keldimi, savdo- sotig'ing yaxshi bo'layapdimi?* – *Mo'min ochiq ko'ngillik bilan sotuvchining qo'llarini silkitdi, - Qancha suvlar oqib o'tdi ko'rishmaganimizdan beri. Xush ko'rdik!*

- *Mo'min chaqqon deb atalgan bu chol shunday sodda, afandife'l edi...*

- *Ko'zi o'tkir-da, bizning bolaning!*

Shunday qilib, o'zbek tilida muloqot insonning ichki, axloqiy fazilatlariga bo'lgan komplimentlarga asoslanadi, ular barcha qayd etilgan komplimentning 22 foizini tashkil qiladi. Ulardan bir oz kam foizi bilan odamning tashqi ko'rinishi o'rin egallagan 20 foiz, va qobiliyatni yoki muayyan kasbni baholovchi komplimentlar 15% Kamdan-kam hollarda ziynatlarga qaratilgan 4%, xonadonga va uy sharoitiga qaratilgan komplimentlar 2% va 9% umumiy baholovchi komplimentlar joy egallagan.

XULOSA

Xulosa qilib shuni, aytishimiz mumkinki ingliz va o'zbek kommunikativ madaniyati juda boy hisoblanib unda komplimentlar juda ko'p qo'llaniladi. Buni biz yuqorida keltirilgan misollarda ko'rishimiz mumkin. Ko'rinib turibdiki har bir madaniyat o'zining xilma-xilligi bilan ajralib turadi. Ingliz kommunikativ madaniyatida kompliment keng qo'llaniladi, ularning madaniyatida kompliment doimiy ishlatiladi. O'zbek kommunikativ madaniyatida esa kompliment kamroq uchraydi bunga bizning mentalitetimiz va dinimiz yo'l qo'ymaydi.

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